

A Note on the Copper Hoards of Jharkhand

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Abstract:

The term “Copper Hoard” refers to a number of copper implements were discovered occasionally, at a place, generally in the form of hoards, while ploughing a field or making a road. Copper hordes of Chota Nagpur, as well as Jharkhand, are unique and characteristically distinct from the other finds. The Earliest evidence of a copper hoard consists of five rough and unfinished copper celts, four of the five now are stored in the Indian Museum, and was found at Kaharbari in Pachamba. Though the chronology and the authorship of the Copper Hoard of Jharkhand as well as India are still being debated. However, on the basis of researches of the previous scholars as well as others, it can be suggested that Copper Hoard people probably also belong to the eastern part of India, i.e., present political boundary of Jharkhand, Orissa, Bihar, and West Bengal, where they had originated independently straight from the Stone Age culture without influence by any

other cultures. They then later moved further west, though the cause of movement is not clear it may be for more resources or another, where they could be in contact with the OCP using people as well as late Harappan people without changing their basic identity but they upgraded their weapons and tools according to the requirement of the new environment to fit with the changed habitats.

Key Words: Copper Hoards, Jharkhand, Chotanagpur, Celt, Anthropomorphic Figure, Asur.

Introduction

The term “Copper Hoard” refers to a number of copper implements were discovered occasionally, at a place, generally in the form of hoards, while ploughing a field or making a road, since 1822 when for the first time a copper hoard was reported from Bithur in Kanpur in the form of copper tools and weapons. After the first discovery, few such hoards have come to light. Accumulating all the finds a region could be marked easily where such hoards have been found frequently. In our sub-continent we have such finds extending from Rajasthan in the west to Bengal and Odisha in the east, and Haryana from the north to Karnataka in the south, even we have found such hoards from Shalozen in Pakistan (Jain 2006), Baluchistan, and previous North West Frontier Province (Brown 1915). But regarding this region, a point is to be mentioned that their concentrations are mostly in the Middle Ganga valley and its peripheral areas, i.e., Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Bengal, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, and Parts of Madhya Pradesh. So far, among the reported

copper hoards (Figure 1), Gungeria is the biggest containing four hundred twenty-four copper objects with one hundred and two thick silver sheets.

Among the reported sites mention may be made of Bisauli (Lal 1951), Rajpur Parsu (Lal 1951), Saipai (Lal 1971-72), Bahadrabad (Krishnadeva 1969), Sherajpur, Chandausi, Khurdi, Sirthauli, Baharia, and Nasirpur. Tools and implements recovered from the copper hoards include Flat Celt, i.e., flat surface on both the side with sharp and wide cutting edge and comparatively thin butt end; Hatches also known as *parasu*, i.e., a small object look likes same as a flat celt, but the butt portion is rectangular and attached with a both side notched head; Harpoon, i.e., a mid-ribbed sword having barbs with curved armed and pointed backward; Antennae Sword, i.e., a large sword with bifurcated hilts; Shouldered Celt, i.e., having an elongated broad blade at the top and take a shape similar of a shoulder and toward the end appear likes a neck; Bar Celt, i.e., Celt having parallel side bars with a crescentric cutting edge but the butt end is pointed; Double Edged Celt or Double Shouldered Celt, i.e., oval shape with two circular cuts one on each side towards the bottom, thus they look like double shouldered Celt; Pick-axe, i.e., a new type generally found in the eastern region, it is convex at the bottom and flat at the top; Hooked Spear Head, i.e., similar like antennae sword but small in size and a hook is attached with the narrow handle; and Anthropomorphic figure, i.e., a human shaped figure with incurved hands, spread out legs, and a convex projected part indicating head.

Figure. 1: The location map shows the reported Copper Hoards Sites in Indian Subcontinent. (A) Indicates the Google earth image of the area. (B) Indicates the state-wise distribution of the Copper Hoards Sites in India. One destined site (21) is located in Pakistan. The sites have been extracted from the published literatures.

Figure 2: Bar Celts found from Hami village in the Palamau District in Jharkhand (All the Celts are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museum).

Copper hoards of Chota Nagpur, as well as Jharkhand, are unique and characteristically distinct from the other finds (A. Ghosh 1989; I. Dhar 1997; S.P. Sukla 1997; P.K. Agarwal 1967; P.L. Gupta n.d). The Earliest evidence of a copper hoard consists of five rough and unfinished copper celts, four of the five now are stored in the Indian Museum, was found at Kaharbari in Pachamba (Now in Hazaribagh District) in 1870. R. B. Foote mentioned about a celt which was given to him collected near Bargunda old copper Mines.¹ S.C. Roy (Roy 1916) in 1916 found a number of copper celts from Ranchi district and in around 1915 he further unearthed a number of copper objects with a few shouldered celts from the so called “Asura” graveyards. C.H. Bompas described three copper double edged celts which he secured along the border of Jharkhand and Orissa (Bompas 1916). A. Campbell (Campbell 1916) noted twenty-three copper objects of which six shouldered celts and one anthropomorphic figure collected in between the hilly region of Pareshnath and Barakar River. He also reported a dozen of copper Axe heads dug out by a coolie at the village Kolbarti during construction of a road along boundary of Hazaribagh district. He described;

This is a range of low hills running almost due east from Pareshnath to Pakhuria in the north of Dhanbad Subdivision. North of this range of hills is the Barakar River, all the axe heads have so far been found in the stretch of country between hills and Barakar river...about two years ago the great find took place. This consisted a dozen magnificent specimens, which were dug up by

¹ In 1887 when Foote visited his friend Dr. Saisses, the Manager of Giridih Coal Mines, he gave Bruce Foote a flat celt and a ring. These were found thirty years earlier at Bargunda, near the old copper mines.

coolies engaged in making road of the boundary of Hazaribagh district. They were found in one lot about a foot below the surface...the axe head of various sizes, of which I have one perfect specimen weight only half a seer, and it resemblance shape a modern American axe-head...The method of manufacturing these axe heads seem to have been to run the metal into a mould, of the shape of, but thicker and smaller than, to finished articles. It was then bitten out to the required thickness (Campbell 1916.)

Coggin Brown (Brown 1915) reported a copper celt and another twenty-one copper axe heads which were carried to him and also was told that those were discovered from Palamau (Figure 4) and Bartoli (Figure 5) (Ranchi district) respectively. We would like to quote his own words;

It seems to have been roughly cast and then beaten into its present shape; the hammer marks are still visible. The cutting edge has been injured by hammering and filing, probably since it was found. The form is very primitive one and closely imitate a well-known stone model. It is related to the certain flat forms from the Gungeria hoard, though it has not got their flatness or fine finish. I am inclined to regard it rather as a link between them and some certain rough specimens found in Hazaribagh. Implements compose of partially pure copper have now been found at 18 sites in Northern India, including the present specimens. Eight of these are in the Upper Ganga valley, three in Bengal, 1 in the Central Provinces, 2 in Baluchistan, 1 in the North West Frontier Province, 1 in Kurran, which was only sent to me last week by Sir John Marshall.

Besides previous finds a number of eminent researchers also have collected such copper hoards and related objects throughout from Jharkhand, i.e., a copper celt in 1910 from Saguna (Figure 4) and seventeen bar celts (Figure 2) with six flat celts (Figure 3) from Hami in Palamau district; five flat celts from Dargama, a flat celt from Bandhu (Figure 7), two flat celt from Kamlewa, a flat celt from Bichna (Figure 4), and two flat celts from unknown villages (Figure 7) in Ranchi district; a shouldered celt from Kera (Figure 4), three shouldered celts from Bardugua (P.S. Chakulia) (Figure 4, 7), and six shouldered celts from Andhari in Singhbhum district; three shouldered celts from Kaharbari in Hazaribagh district; two copper shouldered celts from Chandsai (Figure 6) in Santhal Pargana district; a copper object from Bishuadih, a dozen copper axe heads in various shapes from Kolbarti, and a shouldered celt by Edward Gail and another one from two unknown places in Dhanbad district (Figure 4, 7); seven shouldered celts from Birni, Giridih (Figure 11); and another five celts (three in the Ranchi Museums and two in the Patna Museum) from two unknown places (Figure 7, 13, 14; table 1)

An attempt has been made in this paper to compare the implements which have been found from Jharkhand district, now are stored in Patna museum, to the copper implements which have been secured from various sites in the sub-continent (Figure 6, 7). The bar celt, collected from Jharkhand, are generally made of parallel side bars with a crescentic cutting edge and the butt end is pointed. The upper side of these celts is broader than the lower has a pointed butt. From their present feature, one side even and another uneven, one can easily assume that they are made in the

open mould by pouring the melted metal (Figure 2). Bar celt also reported from Rajpur Parsu and Gungeria. Bar celts of Rajpur Parsu are flat rectangular band without any crescentic cutting edge, but the bar celts of Jharkhand are same as found from Gungeria, except a little dissimilarity, e.g., bar celts of Gungeria having a protruding knob at the top (Brown 1915)

Figure 3: Flat Celt found from Hami village in Palamau District in Jharkhand, India (All the Celts are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museum).

Flat celts are moulded in the open mould and then finished with hammering – marks of hammering can be seen on the surfaces (Table 1). These are generally sub-triangular in shape with a slightly rounded corner and size varies from twelve to twenty centimetres. Flat celts of similar shape are known from a number of sites, but have a uniform and balanced shape with sharp edged bevelled from both sides and a little thicker than found from this region. Above all, the celt from Saguna is unique, it is a hammered piece having an apex at the centre from which it is bevelled at all the sides, and look similar with a Palaeolithic handaxe, except the material (Figure 4)

Shouldered celt was also describe as “splayed –Out” celt by Col. Gordon. The shouldered celts which were collected from Manbhum have thicker in fabric and were produced by without hammering. The neck is short and curved towards the shouldered, but erstwhile long and bent neck celts are also found from the other districts. Shouldered celts are also reported from other regions, but they have a long and straight neck with thin fabric and finished with hammering.

Double shouldered celt which is rare and found only from Jharkhand, Orissa, and from the area which are attached with Jharkhand border. These are oval in shape with two circular cuts on each side towards the bottom, and one shoulder being smaller than the other. These objects are so peculiar that scholars have sometimes confused about their nature. Col. Gordon related them to the historical period while D.P. Agarwal pronounced “there is no evidence to relate them to the copper hoard”, although he was unable to give strong evidence of his words. Except for the three

pieces found in Odisha, another six pieces of the same size, more or less, were recovered with other copper hoard objects, which may reflect that they are associated with the copper hoard.

Figure 4: Shouldered Celt, Flat Celt, Shouldered Celt, Shouldered Celt, Shouldered Celt, and Flat Celt found from Bardugua in Singhbhum District; an Unknown Place in Ranchi District; Kera in Singhbhum District; an unknown place in Dhanbad District; Bardugua in Singhbhum District; and Saguna in Palamau District respectively (All the materials are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museum).

The Pick-Axe is a new type which already has been mentioned above. It is convex at the bottom, and flat at the top. It also bears several wavy lines on the surfaces which indicate blooming when metal was at the molten stage.

Anthropomorphic figures had been recovered from Gungeria, Bisauli, Sirthauli, and Sheorajpur. Smith (Smith 1905) suggested that those might have been used as a religious object. Yule (Yule 1985) suggested a “cultic interpretation for them”. According to Lal (Lal 1951) that could have been used as “religious or utilitarian”. Dikshit (Dikshit 1968), Shukla (Shukla 1997), and R.C. Agarwal (Agarwal 1980) identified it with the proto- type of *Sani Deva*. Jayakar (Jayakar 1982) suggested “a symbol of fertility”. While Sharma (Sharma n.d) identified it as *nandipada* symbol. Deshpande (Deshpande 1969) and Das Gupta (Gupta 1975) related it with the *vajra* and *vedic-vajra* respectively. Godden (Godden 1958) and Pant (Pant 1989) interpreted it as a multipurpose weapon having hammering and cutting properties. S.P. Gupta (Gupta 1963) seeks to affiliate those with the “ancestors of the people”. Allchin (Allchin n.d) and M.P. Joshi (Joshi 1995-96) suggested *parasu* and *parasu purusha* respectively. D.P. Agarwal (Agarwal 1971) argued that these could have been used as missiles or a boomerang. Sankalia (Sankalia 1974) has questioned Agarwal’s interpretation and denoted “such a heavy and complicated weapon for bringing down birds is in every way uneconomical, and not expected from such unsophisticated folk. All over the world, and through the ages, much more simple methods have been employed which are still in use”. However, an anthropomorphic figure was found from Dhanbad district (Ancient Manbhum)

(Figure 7) which Campbell primarily identified as a monkey figure. The figure has stumpy legs and hands with two eyes which represent through two circular engraved lines. The male organ of the figure is prominent which was seen never in any other anthropomorphic figure before. C.P. Sinha (Sinha n.d.) identified it with a male anthropomorphic figure of chalcolithic phase. One thing is clear from the Dhanbad figure, whatsoever we are presently named an anthropomorphic or any other, that the people anyhow tried to reshape a proto-type of human form through their artistic activities to fulfil any particular purpose or need. P.K. Agrawala also stated his view about the Dhanbad figure and concluded;

Figure 5: Flat Celts found from Bartola village in the Ranchi District in Jharkhand, India (All the Celts are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museum).

Figure 6: Flat Celt found from RajpurParsu in Bijnore district in Uttar Pradesh; Flat Celt found from RajpurParsu in Bijnore district in Uttar Pradesh; Flat Celt found from RajpurParsu in Bijnore district in Uttar Pradesh; Shouldered Celt found from Chandsai village in the former SanthalPargana District in Jharkhand; Shouldered Celt found from Chandsai village in the former SanthalPargana District in Jharkhand (All the artefacts are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museums)

“.. the anthropomorphic shapes form a unique themselves from the Gangetic basin. Nowherelse in the world such object are found. They are named anthropomorphic figures only for convenience’s sake as they seem to ‘represent a human form with straddled legs and, incurved arms’”. But their purpose whereas religious of otherwise is highly doubtful. On these few problems the piece described here from the Patna Museum Collection throws a variable light. From it there can be no doubt that is represent a human figure and moreover that of a male since the genital portion is clearly represented. It shows a vertical rendition of a male figure, though crudely made. Yet it is certainly of a high merit as regards ideographic representation. A comparison of this with the Sirthuali or Basauli ‘Anthropomorphic’ leaves no doubt that the latter class of representation also intended human figure in a similar attitude and conception of stylisation. How these figures lead to the well-known *Srivastu* symbol of early art is summarily illustrated here (Agarwala 1967-68).

Chronology of the copper hoard was not decided as most of these were chance find and mainly due to its confinement to a particular region. B.B. Lal in 1950 for the first time associated the copper hoard with the people using Ochre Coloured Pottery (OCP) on the basis of the excavation at Bisauli and Rajpur Parsu, where copper hoard and OCP were found together. M.C. Joshi (Joshi 1971-72) discarded Lal view and noted, “the copper hoard tools indicate the use of highly refine and complicated copper technology, whereas the standard of economy reflected in the excavated materials from the chalcolithic sites appears to be very poor. In his opinion, these

find implements could not have been made by people of ordinary or ordinary culture and might have belonged to earlier copper Bronze Age”. A fragment of anthropomorphic figure from Lothal, although the identification is controversial, a shouldered celt from Navdatoli, and a small Antenna sword from Chandoli have forced scholars in establishing the link between the two cultures – though the association of the two culture cannot be ruled out. On this point V.D. Misra (Misra 2002) argues, “the Harappan cultural zone was arid in nature whereas the copper hoard in the Upper Ganga valley lay in a different climatic zone having higher rainfall and dense forestation, and it is thus quite possible that the letter Harappan, after having left the Indus region, invented new type of tools to adjust themselves to new ecological situation”. Whereas S.P. Gupta (Gupta 1963) believed that “there is, therefore, every possibility that these two cultures moving within the same area in opposite direction somewhere met each other. The traces of influences in the chalcolithic cultures are due to possible contract.” D.P. Agarwal (Agarwal 1969) supported Gupta’s view and denoted;

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Figure 7: Flat Celt found from Bandua village in Ranchi District in Jharkhand; Shouldered Celt found from Mayurbhanj District in Odish; Shouldered Celt found from Bardugua village in the Singhbhum District in Jharkhand; Flat celt found from an unknown place in the Ranchi District in Jharkhand; Shouldered Celt found from an unknown place in the Dhanbad District in Jharkhand; Shouldered Celt found from an unknown place in the Chotanagpur Area in Jharkhand (All the artefacts in this figure are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museums).

**Figure 8: An anthropomorphic figure found from the ancient Manbhum District in the present Jharkhand
(This figure is now stored in the Store of the Patna Museum)**

Copper Hoards form a class themselves, unrelated to Harappan or the Chalcolithic tradition. The evidences show that Harappan culture and the Copper Hoard culture were two independent cultures devoid of any direct cultural transmission. The types shows that the copper hoard tools were fashioned out for a hunting and nomadic life. Centres of Harappan and Copper Hoards culture were divided by an area of dense monsoonal forest. Copper Hoard culture probably originated in the Chota Nagpur Figureau which were reach in copper minerals

A. Ghosh (Ghosh 1989) also said;

In view of the absence of copper ores in the doab and the occurrence of only the simpler form of tools near the copper producing areas of Bihar, in contrast to the developed form found in w. Uttar Pradesh , it has been summarised that the hoards originated in Bihar and developed in the western region. As a corollary, it has also been hypothesized originally their makers were the ancestor of the present day Mundas, who at one time came into contract with the Indo-Aryans coming from the west, but the theory has not been established.

In the case of Jharkhand, as far as evidences are concerned, more than twenty Copper Hoards sites have so far been reported with sophisticated copper weapons, implements, and other copper objects. After carefully study of the implements Coggin Brown (Brown 1915) postulated;

Before 1000 B.C. the place now taken by iron was occupied by copper which for some milleniums earlier had supplied the materials from which implements and weapons were made. These flat

copper celts which have been found at so many sites in Northern India are obviously copies of Neolithic Patterns in stone, and although their flat shape may not prove as much as it would in Europe, owing to the absence in India, as far as we know at present, of direct evolution from the flat through the winged to the socketed forms, a high antiquity is claimed for them. Similar examples found in Ireland are dated 1800-2000 B.C.; though I do not think this can be used as an argument in fixing the period of the Indians one. I believe with Vincent Smith that all Indian copper implements are extremely old, and must be dated previously to 1080 B.C.

Figure 9 Polished Stone Tools, Copper Objects and a Double Shouldered Celt were collected by S.C. Roy from so called “Asura Graveyard” in Ranchi District. The Double Shouldered Celt which we noticed in the assemblages of Asura, now stored in Patna Museum, but its provenance is not clear as the accession no. written on the object blurred completely.

Figure 10: In this figure we are comparing Bat Celts and Flat Copper Celts with the polished Stone Tools (length varies from 10 – 20 centimetres) which were collected by S.C. Roy, Anderson, and Breeching from the Ranchi District, Singhbhum District, and Santhal Pargana region respectively (All the antiquities are now stored in the Store of the Patna Museums).

Figure 11: Copper Shouldered Celts found from Birni, Giridih, Jharkhand and now are displayed in the Prehistoric Gallery of Ranchi State Museum.

Though the chronology and the authorship of the Copper Hoard of Jharkhand as well as India are still being debated, some points in this context need to be noted with all respect to the views of the previous scholars: Firstly; OCPs and Copper Hoards are not associated in Jharkhand

– Hoards have been found here without OCP. Secondly; the view that the Harappan were the ancestor of this culture is not acceptable because we have so far only few copper implements, in the forms and types, in comparison to what we have recovered in the peripheral areas of Mid-Ganga valley as well as Jharkhand. Third; Indo-Aryans too may not have been associated with these Hoards, because, as the Rigveda suggests, their area of influence was mainly confined to “Sapta Sindhu”. Fourth; if the Antenna swords and harpoons are considered as a more advanced tools type, found mainly from western part of Uttar Pradesh and yet not been reported from Jharkhand, then what our view would be about Double Edged Celts or Double Shouldered Celts and the unique Anthropomorphic figure – yet to be found from other places. In fact those should be considered more or less advanced copper implements and ought to be placed within the same bracket of technology which produced Antennae Swords and Harpoons. Fifthly; we should not forget the plentiful copper materials, more than a thousand, including shouldered celts associated with polished stone tools and iron objects (Figure 9), collected and illustrated by S.C. Roy from so called “Asura” graveyards and C.P. Sinha and A. S. Roy (Sinha and Roy 2018) also described these with the graveyard materials under the uprighted large unhewn stones. Sixthly; it is accepted that Chota Nagpur region was the main source and prime centre of copper production (Ball, 1869), A copper thrust zone of the Achaean Period (Mukhopadhyay, 1980) is noticed through the middle of the district. A map of the Copper Shear Zone (Figure 12) is also prepared based on the geological map of the Geological Survey of India and Mineralogical Map of Govt. of Jharkhand. It is also important to note that the copper tools and weapons found here are mostly prototype of polished

stone tools which have been frequently reported from Chakradharpur, Sanjoy valley, and other regions in Jharkhand (Agarwal 1999; Brown 1915; Sinha and Roy 2018) (Figure 10). And Lastly; we always have an instinct that we have ignored the technology of our natives without any consciousness of their nature, but in the present context it would not be possible, because if they had the technology to produce the advanced Double Shouldered Celt and more developed Anthropomorphic figure, *Nem Com*, then they could have easily produced other tools and objects. However, on the basis of researches of the previous scholars as well as others, it can be suggested that Copper Hoard people probably also belong to the eastern part of India, i.e., present political boundary of Jharkhand, Orissa, Bihar, and West Bengal, where they had originated independently straight from the Stone Age culture without influence by any other cultures. They then later moved further west, though the cause of movement is not clear it may be for more resources or another, where they could be in contact with the OCP using people as well as late Harappan people without changing their basic identity, but they upgraded their weapons and tools according to the requirement of the new environment to fit with the changed habitats.²

² The Copper Hoard people are hunting-gathering people as seen from the type of artefacts, whereas the OCP people had as sedentary life and from the evidences of numerous types of pottery, one can assume that they had started agriculture and were economically well established. There is no doubt that the two cultures at one time met with each other at one place, but it seem that mostly they kept their own identity as we find OCP and Copper Hoard at the same place but no in a single assemblage (Indrani Dhar 1980).

Figure 12: Map showing the Copper Shear Zone along the River Suvarnarekha in Jharkhand.

Figure 13: Copper Hoards Sites in Jharchand State of India. The documents are mostly (11 sites) collected from Patna Museum Accession Register. Documents of 2 sites have been collected from the published references. One recent copper mine has been identified in this area which indicates the availability of copper ore naturally.

Figure 14: Copper Plain and Shouldered Celts, Collected by S.C. Roy somewhere in Jharkhand and a few years ago were donated by his son P.C. Roy to the Ranchi State Museum along with a Tibetan Vajrasatta image.

Table 1: Illustration of the Figures

Sl. no.	Figure no.	Object (Left to Right)	Measurement (in Centimetres)	Provenance
1	6	Flat Celt	18.4 x 10.5	Rajpur Parsu, Bijnore, U.P
2		Flat Celt	17.1 x 12.2	Rajpur Parsu, Bijnore, U.P
3		Flat Celt	22.2 x 17.4	Rajpur Parsu, Bijnore, U.P
4		Shouldered Celt	25.5 x 23.5	Chandsai, Santhal Pargana District, Jharkhand
5		Shouldered Celt	25 x 24	Chandsai, Santhal Pargana District, Jharkhand
6	2	Bar Celt	41 x 6	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
7		Bar Celt	43.2 x 6	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
8		Bar Celt	51 x 7	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
9		Bar Celt	49.2 x 7	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
10		Bar Celt	51 x 5	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
11		Bar Celt	35 x 4	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
12		Bar Celt	47 x 4.8	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
13		Bar Celt	41 x 5.9	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
14		Bar Celt	62 x 5.5	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
15		Bar Celt	43 x 5.5	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
16	3	Flat Celt	17 x 13.1	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
18		Flat Celt	17 x 14.4	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
19		Flat Celt	17.5 x 14.3	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
20		Flat Celt	17.6 x 14.4	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand

21		Flat Celt	16.8 x 13.6	Hami, Palamau District, Jharkhand
22	4	Shouldered Celt	25.7 x 23.5	Bardugua, Singhbhum District, Jharkhand
23		Flat Celt	14.2 x 10.8	From an Unknown Place, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
24		Shouldered Celt	16.9 x 14.3	Kera, Singhbhum
25		Shouldered Celt	25.2 x 19.1	Dhanbad District, Jharkhand
26		Shouldered Celt	27.2 x 24.2	Bardugua, Singhbhum District, Jharkhand
27		Flat Celt	18.5 x 15.5	Saguna, Palamau District, Jharkhand
28	5	Flat Celt	14.4 x 11.5	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
29		Flat Celt	14.8 x 10.5	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
30		Flat Celt	15.5 x 11.4	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
31		Flat Celt	13.9 x 10.3	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
32		Flat Celt	14 x 10.5	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
33		Flat Celt	17.5 x 11	Bartola, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
34	7	Flat Celt	15.5 x 12.8	Bandua, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
36		Shouldered Celt	23.3 x 20.5	Mayurbhanj District, Odisha
37		Shouldered Celt	26.5 x 23.5	Bardugua, Singhbhum District, Jharkhand
38		Flat celt	14.6 x 11.1	An unknown place, Ranchi District, Jharkhand
39		Shouldered Celt	17.6 x 16.7	Dhanbad District, Jharkhand
40		Shouldered Celt	23.7 x 17	Chota Nagpur Area
41	8	An anthropomorphic figure	18 centimetre in length	Dhanbad District, Jharkhand
42	9	Polished Stone Tools, Copper Objects and one Double Shouldered Celt, S.C. Roy collected from So called Asura Graveyard in Ranchi District. The Double		

		Shouldered Celt which we noticed in the assemblages of Asura, now stored in Patna Museum, but its provenance is not clear as the accession no blurred completely.
43	10	In this Figure we compare bat celts and flat celts with the polished stone tools (length varies from 10 – 20 centimetres) which collected by S.C. Roy, Anderson, and Walsh from Ranchi District, Singhbhum District, and Santhal Pargana region respectively

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